

Embracing alternative paths:Strateguc recommendations for Childless couples in Rural Communities

Mina Margaret Ogbanga,PhD

Abstract

The study examined the strategic recommendations to couples faced with the issue of childlessness in the society. One objective and one research question were raised for the study. The descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A population of 160,301 women in 65 communities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State was used. A sample of 100 women from 5 communities was used and this was done via multi-stage sampling technique of Random sampling technique and Proportionate sampling technique. The questionnaire titled "Socio-cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples Questionnaire (SICMCQ)" was used as instrument to collect relevant data. The instrument was validated by some experts and its reliability was tested for to be 0.75. The data collected, were analyzed using frequency, mean and percentage for the research questions and Chi-square was used to test for the hypotheses. The findings from the study showed that data in the table above displayed the mean responses of the women on the strategic recommendations to couples faced with the issue of childlessness in the society. From the analysis done, all the items with respective mean scores of 3.4, 3.37, 3.41 and 3.45 were accepted because their mean scores are above the criterion-mean score of 2.5. Based on the grand mean score obtained at 3.41, it can therefore be deduced that strategies such as awareness creation, provision of needed facilities as well as policy formulation can be highly effective towards curbing the issues of childlessness among married couples. It was recommended among others that policies should be generated towards protecting the rights of couples in the society, regardless of what they might be facing.

Introduction

Evidence from history has it that, reproduction has always been essential in the continuation of the human race. For those couples who wish to build a life together, they Ianna Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies, Volume 5, Number 1 June, 2023 24 often have a desired vision for their future and typically desire to have children of their own (Asemota, 2015). In most cultures, pregnancy and parenting are seen as major, integral and desirable steps of life progression. Achieving the role of a parent is a top priority for many men and women, and this ideal has been instilled in us through multiple generations. Parenthood is essential for attaining personal satisfaction, social validation, reaching full adult status, embracing religions, reinstating identity and achieving mental equilibrium. Reproducing and parenting are both generally considered

fundamental human rights, and a necessary advancement in life stages. For couples without children, the range of emotions can be vast, ranging from a slight sense of disappointment to overwhelming grief (Asemota, 2015).

Worldwide, 5 to 10 percent of couples are presently affected by childlessness (Hayes, 2016). Childlessness experienced by couples at some point of time is reported to be between 8 to 12 percent around the world, affecting nearly 50 to 80 million people and the prevalence is cited to be about 5 percent due to anatomical, genetic, endocrinological and immunological problems (Hayes, 2016.) In India, there are estimated to be between 5 and 10 million infertile couples, and this figure is growing by around 5% every two years. Childlessness is known as being unable to conceive after one year of unprotected sexual intercourse without known reproductive issues. Ayankeye, (2013) argue that children are considered a blessing, and in some societies, they are even seen as a sign of God's approval and blessings for the marriage. Ultimately, it is up to each individual or couple to make the decision on whether or not to have children and how many. However, couples in many African cultures may face immense pressure from family and social groups if they are unable to bear children shortly after their union, which can result in frustration, resentment, and depression (Rasak & Oladipo, 2017) In Nigeria, researchers have studied the prevalence of childlessness through demographic surveys, epidemiological surveys, and clinical observation (Pedro, 2013). The Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey for 2010-2016 reported a primary infertility rate of 22.7% for women aged 15-24 and 7.1% for women aged 25-49 (Tabong et al, 2013). This inability to conceive affects both men and women throughout the nation, leading to distress, depression, discrimination, and ostracism. To cope with the strain of infertility, couples use a variety of strategies such as escape/avoidance tactics, self-control methods, seeking social support, positive reappraisal approaches among other. Jordan and Al-Asadi (2015) suggest that coping strategies are techniques used by individuals to handle difficult situations. Everyone manages stress in their own way and develops tactics over time that prove to be beneficial for their mental health. Coping with childlessness can be especially hard, as it can be seen as a long-term, unpredictable, and (personally or medically) uncontrollable stressor that may be too much for the couple to bear. Doron et al. (2011) observed that individuals dealing with childlessness tend to employ particular coping strategies, such as distancing themselves from reminders of the absence

of children, taking steps to gain a sense of control, attempting to boost their sense of worth through professional accomplishments, trying to make sense of their childlessness, or sharing the burden with others in their social circle..

Aim and Objectives of the Study

To proffer strategic recommendations to couples faced with the issue of childlessness in the society.

Research Question

What are the strategic recommendations to couples faced with the issue of childlessness in the society?

Significance of the Study

To the government; the findings from this study will bring to their notice the deterrent effects of socio-cultural perceptions towards childlessness in the society thereby enabling them to develop policies that will help in reframing them.

Scope of the Study

This study will strictly focus on examining socio-cultural and childlessness impact on married couples in the society. The target population for this study will comprise of married couples in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

Definition of Terms

Childlessness: This refers to the inability of procuring an offspring.

Impact: This refers to the exacerbated influence an entity has on another.

Socio-Cultural Impact: This refers to the influence exerted by the society on another entity socially and culturally.

Married Couples: These are individuals that have decided to imbibe the duty of coming together to live as one legally, traditionally or religiously.

Childlessness among Married Couples in the Society

Childlessness is one aspect of the diversity inherent in contemporary experience of marriage and the family. Childlessness is a concern, partly because of its implications for the maintenance of societies and partly because of its unwanted consequences for individuals (Egharevba, 2020). Like any other social phenomenon, childlessness needs to be understood within historical, social, and cultural circumstances as well as individual and relational characteristics. In industrialized countries, childlessness was more prevalent at the start of the twentieth century than at the end of the twentieth century. It was, however, less conspicuous because it occurred in conjunction with a large family system; that is, where some had four or more children, partly offset the childlessness of others, keeping birth rates relatively high. In the present situation, one reason why the effects of childlessness are now more apparent is that smaller families are more prevalent, with pronounced preferences for two children; relatively few couples have four or more (Rasak & Oladipo, 2017). Childlessness can now make the difference between maintaining population numbers and precipitating long term decline. In marriage, childlessness is one aspect of the diversity inherent in contemporary experience of marriage and the family (Egharevba, 2020). For most of history, childlessness has been regarded as great personal tragedy involving much

emotional pain and grief, especially when it is resulted from failure to conceive or from the death of a child. With this greater diversity, once common pressures for childbearing have given way to greater social acceptance of remaining single or married without children. Before conception was well understood, childlessness was usually blamed on the woman and this in itself added to the high level negative emotional and social effects of childlessness.

Some wealthy families also adopted children as a means of providing heirs in case of childlessness or where no son had been born, the monetary incentives offered by westerners desire for children is so strong that a commercial market in the child laundering business exists (Hollo& Whitehouse, 2014). Nonetheless, childlessness is a concern, partly because of its implications for the maintenance of societies and partly because of its unwanted consequences for individuals. However, societies regard children as the most important asset in every successful marriage and for this reason; childless couples become an object of ridicule in their communities. The dynamics of culture and human relationships have made researchers to observe many influences, manifestations, happenings and occurrences in marriage stability within the Yoruba community (Rasak&Oladipo, 2017). Childlessness is the term for people - men and women - having no children. Childlessness may have personal, social and/or political significance. Approximately 70-80 million couples worldwide are currently infertile () and it can be estimated that tens of millions of couples are primarily infertile or childless (Rasak & Oladipo, 2017). For most people, having children is immensely important; not being able to have children is a major life problem. There is also a large group of women and men, who have children, possibly from a previous relationship, who desperately wants to have another child. A considerable body of research in Western countries has shown that involuntary childlessness has strong psychological consequences.

Theoretical Review***Psychosocial Theory by Erik Erikson***

Psychosocial theory focuses on the nature of self-understanding, social relationships, and the mental processes that support connections between the person and his/her social world. Societies, with their structures, laws, roles, rituals, and sanctions, are organized to guide individual growth toward a particular ideal of mature adulthood. However, every society faces problems when it attempts to balance the needs of the individual with the needs of the group. The theory introduced the concept of normative psychosocial crises, predictable tensions that arise as a result of conflicts between socialization and maturation throughout life.

Psychosocial theory explains changes in self-understanding, social relationships, and one's relationship to society from infancy through later life.

1. Trust vs. Mistrust

The first stage of Erikson's psychosocial development starts at birth and continues to approximately 18 months of age. The principal task is trust versus mistrust. Infants rely solely upon their caregivers; thus, if caregivers are responsive and sensitive to their infant's needs, it helps the infant develop a sense of trust. Apathetic caregivers who do not meet their baby's needs may cause the baby to develop feelings of anxiety, fear and mistrust and see the world as unpredictable. Basic virtue developed: hope.

2. Autonomy vs. Shame and Doubt

The second stage occurs between the ages of 1½ and 3 years. If a child is allowed to develop at their own pace during this stage, they can acquire self-reliance and self-confidence. However, if parents are inconsistent, overcritical, or overprotective, the child may doubt their ability to control themselves and their world. Basic virtue developed: will.

3. Initiative vs. Guilt

The third of Erikson's eight stages of psychosocial development arises during the preschool stage, 3-5 years of age. A child can develop initiative through social interactions, and by planning and commencing in play and other activities. If the child's pursuits fail or are criticized, feelings of self-doubt and guilt may arise. Basic virtue developed: purpose.

4. Industry vs. Inferiority

The fourth stage occurs from ages 5 to 12 years. During this period, a child begins to compare themselves with peers. The child learns to be productive and to accept the evaluation of his or her efforts, and in turn, can develop a sense of accomplishment and pride in their academic work, sports, social activities and home life. If a child feels they do not measure up, feelings of inferiority or incompetence may be established. Basic virtue developed: competency.

Methodology***Research Design***

The design of this study is the descriptive research design. This design is that which employs both qualitative and quantitative data for the proper dissemination of the stated questions that are formulated to dissolve the major purpose for this study. This research design was chosen because

of the purpose of the study to gather information on socio-cultural impact of childlessness on married couples in the society.

Population of the Study

The population for this study will comprise of women present in the 65 communities in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State, which constitutes to a total estimation of 160,301 women (National Population Census, (2008) and World Sex Ratio (2021)).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A multi-stage sampling technique of random sampling technique and proportionate sampling technique will be used for sample selection. Random sampling technique will be used in the selection of 5 communities out of the 65 communities in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in Rivers State. Proportionate sampling technique will then be adopted in the selection of 20 women each in the chosen communities. A total sample of 100 women will then be given and used for the study, as stipulated in the table below:

Table 1: Sample Distribution

S/N	Districts	Sample Chosen
1	Choba	20
2	Rumueme	20
3	Ozuoba	20
4	Rumuokoro	20
5	Rumuiabo	20
Total		100

Instrument for Data Collection

The instrument employed in this study is the questionnaire. It is a 20-item self-structure instrument titled “**Socio-cultural Impact of Childlessness on Married Couples Questionnaire (SICMCQ)**” that will be partitioned into two sections (A and B). Section A will cover the demographic aspect of it, which collects personal information about the respondents, while section B will cover the items, which elicited the responses of the respondents on each of the item statements present. The items are responded to with the aid of 4-point Likert scale of measurement of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

Method of Data Collection

Data will be collected using questionnaires. The researcher will go to the field and meet up with respondents, then hand out the copies of the questionnaire to them. These respondents will be given directives on how to go about the filling of the distributed instrument. After completion, the researcher will proceed to retrieve the distributed instrument immediately.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

Face and content validity of the instrument will be established by giving it to my supervisor and two other lecturers in the Department of Sociology. Their inputs will be ratified further by the supervisor, before its incorporation in the production the final draft of the questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument will be done through the test-retest method. This method is that which involves the administration of the instrument to a selected group of 20 women (outside the sample of the study but within the population of the study) with a separating time difference of 10 days between the two administrations. The responses gotten from the two administrations will then be

compared and correlated through the adoption of Pearson Product Moment Correlation, so as to arrive at the reliability co-efficient index of 0.75.

Method of Data Analysis

The data will be subjected to an analytical procedure with the aid of frequency, mean and percentage for the research questions. Chi-square will be used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The criterion-mean will be calculated for as follows:

Strongly Agree (SA) - 4points

Agree (A) - 3points

Disagree (D) - 2points

Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1point

$$\text{Criterion mean} = \frac{4+3+2+1}{4} = \frac{10}{4} = 2.5$$

The item with a mean score that is up to and above the criterion mean will be “accepted” while the one with a mean score that is below the criterion mean will be “rejected”.

Research Question 4: What are the strategic recommendations to couples faced with the issue of childlessness in the society?

Table 4.6: Mean statistics displaying the strategic recommendations to couples faced with the issue of childlessness in the society

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	$\bar{x}$	Remark
17	Proper educative awareness on the causes of childlessness health-wise for couples.	40 (160)	60 (180)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.4	Accepted
18	Proper dissemination of causes of childlessness towards seeking for a	37	63	0	0		

	different perspective towards it in the society.	(148)	(189)	(0)	(0)	3.37	Accepted
19	Creating avenues for high and effective healthcare diagnosis facilities in the society.	41 (164)	59 (177)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.41	Accepted
20	Creating policies to tackle derogatory remarks against childlessness of individuals in the society.	45 (180)	55 (165)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3.45	Accepted
	Grand Mean					3.41	High

Data in the table above displayed the mean responses of the women on the strategic recommendations to couples faced with the issue of childlessness in the society. From the analysis done, all the items with respective mean scores of 3.4, 3.37, 3.41 and 3.45 were accepted because their mean scores are above the criterion-mean score of 2.5. Based on the grand mean score obtained at 3.41, it can therefore be deduced that strategies such as awareness creation, provision of needed facilities as well as policy formulation can be highly effective towards curbing the issues of childlessness among married couples.

Recommendations

- 1) Policies should be generated towards protecting the rights of couples in the society, regardless of what they might be facing.
- 2) Measures should be directed towards the enhancement of medical facilities in the aide to curb the prevalence of childlessness in the society.

Summary and Conclusion

The study examined the socio-cultural impact of childlessness impact on married couples in the society. It was carried out with stipulated objectives. In actualizing this, several concepts have

being reviewed for the better understanding of both the independent and dependent variables of the study and lots have been gathered childlessness and some factors that affect it and how impactful it can be on couples in the society by linking it socially and culturally. The whole study was compiled under five strategic chapters with each chapter having their inputs to make towards the completion of this work, thereby implying one another as time goes by. With the first chapter covering the background that led to the carrying out of the work, the problem that can be cited as well as the objectives that are hoped to be achieved in the process of going about the tackling of the problems stated and the likes of it; the second chapter reviewing several past works that relates to this study; the third chapter stating the particular methodology that was adopted for the study; the fourth chapter going about the analyzing of the data that has been gathered and collated from the field to determine the purpose etched out for this study to investigate and then the fifth chapter serving as the concluding chapter of the study.

REFERENCES

- Anokye, R., Acheampong, E., Mprah, W. K., Ope, J. O. & Barivure, T. N. (2017). Psychosocial effects of infertility among couples attending St. Michael's Hospital, Jachie-Pranso in the Ashanti Region of Ghana. *BMC Research Notes*, 10(1), 1-5.
- Botwe, B. O., Bamfo-Quaicoe, K., Hunu, E. & Anim-Sampong, S. (2015). Hysterosalpingographic findings among Ghanaian women undergoing infertility work-up: a study at the Korle-Bu Teaching Hospital. *Fertility Research and Practice*, 1(1), 1-6.
- Cui, C., Wang, L. & Wang, X. (2021). Effects of self-esteem on the associations between infertility-related stress and psychological distress among infertile Chinese women: a cross-sectional study. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 14, 1245.
- Dierickx, S., Rahbari, L., Longman, C., Jaiteh, F. & Coene, G. (2018). 'I am always crying on the inside': a qualitative study on the implications of infertility on women's lives in urban Gambia. *Reproductive Health*, 15(1), 1-11.

- Egharevba, O. J. (2020). The Socio-Cultural impact of Childlessness on Married Couples in Egor Local Government Area of Edo State. Nigeria. *FULafia Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(4), 50-65.
- Fehintola, A. O., Fehintola, F. O., Ogunlaja, O. A., Awotunde, T. O., Ogunlaja, I. P. & Onwudiegwu, U. (2017). Social meaning and consequences of infertility in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. *Sudan Journal of Medical Sciences*, 12(2), 63-77.
- Gouni, O., Jarašiūnaitė-Fedosejeva, G., KōmürçüAkik, B., Holopainen, A. & Calleja-Agius, J. (2022). Childlessness: Concept Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(3), 1464.
- HasmanováMarhánková, J. (2015). The changing practices and meanings of grandparenthood. Reflections on the demographical trends and changing representations of ageing. *Sociology Compass*, 9(4), 309-319.
- Hollos, M. & Whitehouse, B. (2014). Women in limbo: life course consequences of infertility in a Nigerian community. *Human Fertility*, 17(3), 188-191.
- Ibisomi, L. & Mudege, N. N. (2014). Childlessness in Nigeria: perceptions and acceptability. *Culture, Health & Sexuality*, 16(1), 61-75.
- Isah, B. A., Yahayah, M., Panti, A. A., Abubakar, S., Shehu, A., Bello, A. S. & Abdulaziz, M. D. (2018). Perceived causes of infertility and its psychosocial effects among women with infertility attending gynaecology clinic in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Teaching Hospital, Sokoto. *IOSR Journal of Dentistry and Medical Sciences*, 17(11), 26-30.
- Ishola, F., Owolabi, O. & Filippi, V. (2017). Disrespect and abuse of women during childbirth in Nigeria: A systematic review. *PloS One*, 12(3), e0174084.
- Mbachaga, D. J. & Akaa, A. A. (2015). Infertility in marriage and its impact on the family: James Alachi's *Your precious Ihotu*. *Creative Artist: A Journal of Theatre and Media Studies*, 9(1), 66-83.
- Mudiare, P. E. U. (2013). Abuse of the aged in Nigeria: Elders also cry. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 3(9), 79-87.
- Musa, R., Ramli, R., Yazmie, A. W. A., Khadijah, M. B. S., Hayati, M. Y., Midin, M., ... & Ravindran, A. (2014). A preliminary study of the psychological differences in infertile couples and their relation to the coping styles. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 55, S65-S69.
- Mustafa, M., Sharifa, A. M., Hadi, J., Izzam, E. & Aliya, S. (2019). Male and female infertility: causes, and management. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences*, 18, 27-32.

- Nnadi, I. (2013). Son preference-A violation of women's human rights: A case study of Igbo custom in Nigeria. *Journal of Politics & Law*, 6, 134.
- Nwaomah, E. N. & Dube, S. (2018). Involuntary childlessness and its socio-cultural impact on married couples: Implications for pastoral counseling. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 3(10), 410-414.
- Obiyo, I. D. (2016). Impact of Childlessness on Marriage.(A study of married couples in Lowa community, Imo State). *International Journal of Religious and Cultural Practice*, 2(1), 9-17.
- Ogbanga, M. M., & Sharma, S. N. (2024). Climate Change and Mental Heat. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13284459>
- Ojedokun, I. M. (2019). Influence of family and spiritual supports on coping with infertility among couples in Ibadan Oyo State Nigeria. *African Journal for the Psychological Studies of Social Issues*, 22(3), 205-216.
- Okantey, G. N. O., Adomako, E. B., Baffour, F. D. & Lim, D. (2021). Sociocultural implications of infertility and challenges in accessing assisted reproductive technology: Experiences of couples from two health facilities in southern Ghana. *Marriage & Family Review*, 57(5), 375-396.
- Okin, S. M. (2015). Justice, gender, and the family. In *Justice, Politics, and the Family* (pp. 63-87). Routledge.
- Okpan, S. O. & Otega, O. (2021). Socio-cultural consequences of being childless; perspectives across Africa and Europe. *Nigerian Journal of Social Problems and Social Policy Review*, 1(2).
- Rasak, B. & Oladipo, P. (2017). Childlessness and its socio-cultural implication on married couples within some selected Yoruba communities in South-West Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Social Sciences & Humanities Research*, 5(1), 42-54.
- Saumet, J., Petropanagos, A., Buzaglo, K., McMahon, E., Warraich, G. & Mahutte, N. (2018). No. 356-egg freezing for age-related fertility decline. *Journal of obstetrics and gynaecology Canada*, 40(3), 356-368.
- Schenk, J. L. (2018). Principles of maximizing bull semen production at genetic centers. *Animal*, 12(s1), s142-s147.

Upadhyay, Y., Chhabra, A. & Nagar, J. C. (2020). A women infertility: an overview. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development*, 8(2), 99-106.

Wando, O. A. (2017). *Knowledge, attitude and socio-cultural beliefs and practices among infertile persons in Kisumu County, Kenya* (Doctoral dissertation, Moi University).

Youens, D., Halkett, G., Wright, C., O'Connor, M., Schofield, P., Jefford, M., ... & RT Prepare project team. (2019). Assessing the cost-effectiveness of RT Prepare: A radiation therapist-delivered intervention for reducing psychological distress prior to radiotherapy. *Psycho-Oncology*, 28(5), 1110-1118.